

SHANKAR GOYAL, *History and Historiography of the Age of Harṣa* (Kusumanjali Prakashan, Jodhpur, 1992). Pp. xx + 343. Rs 350.00.

Dr Shankar Goyal's *History and Historiography of the Age of Harṣa* makes a welcome departure from quite a few books which already exist on the topic. Most other treatments of Harṣa simply concentrate on narrating his history. Dr Goyal, however, goes behind the scene, so to say, and devotes the first part (pp. 1-94) of his book, covering nearly hundred pages to a critical examination of the historiographic approaches of different scholars who have written on Harṣa. This is in itself an original and valuable contribution not only to studies on Harṣa, but to ancient Indian studies in general.

In the second part (pp. 95-239), Dr Goyal begins by tracing the political background of the rise of the Puṣyabhūti dynasty and goes on to examine its early history culminating in the brief career of Rājyavardhana. Among other things, he argues that Harṣavardhana was involved in the murder of his brother Rājyavardhana. He goes into several doubts raised by earlier scholars like Professor R. C. Majumdar and articulated more explicitly by Professors D. Devahuti and S. R. Goyal before arriving at his own conclusion.

The career of Harṣa is narrated and discussed in detail and the controversial question of Harṣa's empire receives full attention. Harṣa's relations with China and Iran are also discussed and the evidence of Ajanta paintings is taken into account, but discounted.

The third part (pp. 243-300) describes the state of society, administration and culture in the age of Harṣa. It discusses the emergence of feudalism and the transition to the medieval period. It attempts to analyse the implications of feudalism in various aspects of social and cultural life and ends with a fresh estimate of the greatness and limitations of Harṣa (part four, pp. 303-28).

The book with its novel perspective and analytical acumen should undoubtedly be welcome to students and scholars.

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VIJAY KUMAR THAKUR, *Historiography of Indian Feudalism* (Janaki Prakashan, Patna, 1989). Pp. xxviii + 147. Rs 200.00.

Here is "a critique to all such formulations which reject the models of Indian feudalism" (p. vii). For this the author begins—as one must—with his own understanding of the term "feudalism". This, we discover, is a disarming move. By citing the multiple and an altogether bewildering range of definitions of feudalism (pp. x-xx, 2-7), he is led on to the belief that it would be "futile" and "unhistorical" to "standardise the concept of feudalism in the world context" (p. 5; also pp. ix, xix). At the same time he is aware of the need for "identifying some of the primary and basic traits of feudalism in the universal context" (p. 5). Without clarifying the distinction between the "standard concept of feudalism" and "the basic traits of feudalism" he discovers the traits in the features—constraints on peasants' freedom, a class of landlords, "closed" economic units, a system of government, etc.—which R. S. Sharma and B. N. S. Yadava associate with *Indian* feudalism (pp. 6-7). Having thus cleared the conceptual hurdles, Thakur proceeds to clear the empirical hurdles that come in the way of Indian feudalism.

Agreeing wholeheartedly with Sharma's measured critique of D. C. Sircar ("Indian Feudalism Retouched", *The Indian Historical Review*, Vol. I, No. 2, March 1974, pp. 320-30), Thakur states that he would take up only "the new issues raised by Sircar" (p. 7), that is, those after Sircar's *Political and Administrative System in Ancient and Medieval India* (Delhi, 1974). Since Sircar does not seem to do so, repeating mostly the things he said earlier, with some additional references, Thakur is understandably constrained to repeat in good measure the arguments of Sharma in the works cited by him (those of U. Thakur, K. K. Thaplyal, S. K. Maity, etc.), with some additional details (pp. 7-22). But his judgement on Sircar about the *rūpakas* of Kṛṣṇarāja seems hasty (pp. 12-13), for these coins have long been known from not just all over Maharashtra but also from Malwa and Rajasthan (V. V. Mirashi, *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. IV, Pt 1, pp. xlvi, clxxx-clxxxii). Moreover, the importance of salt trade in a pre-capitalist society must not be underestimated, as Thakur does (pp. 21-22). The scale of the trade in salt—consumed by all and daily—would arguably be much higher than that in any other, yet—thanks again to its universal consumption—the trade would normally not contribute significantly to urban concentrations of population as distinct from rural ones.

The author is on surer grounds in discussing urban centres (pp. 22-25, 47-57, 74-77), on the decline of which he did some original research in his doctoral thesis. Here he presents further fresh material on the archaeological evidence for the decline, including of those centres which were cited by B. D. Chattopadhyaya to show the continuity of the sites into the early medieval period ("Trade and Urban Centres in Early Medieval North India", *IHR*, Vol. I, No. 2, September 1974, pp. 203-19). He stands to profit, however, from R. S. Sharma's *Urban Decay in Early India, c. 300 - c. 1000* (Delhi, 1987).

B. D. Chattopadhyaya's writings on trade and urbanization in early medieval India differ *in quality* from those of D. C. Sircar. Quite unlike Sircar's polemic against urban decline, Chattopadhyaya has been grappling with the evidence for both the decline as well as the survival of urban centres. He has no doubt been sceptical about the explanations that are offered for the urban decline, but has never denied the fact of decline. His attempt to "examine closely to what extent and in what precise form trade and urbanism survived in the post-Gupta period" (*IHR*, Vol. I, No. 2, p. 207) has frequently been misunderstood in the climate of polarized opinion, even by the alert Irfan Habib (*The Journal of Peasant Studies*, Vol. 12, Nos 2 and 3, 1985, p. 52, fn. 6). It is indeed attempts such as those of Chattopadhyaya and Tarafdar—rather than flat denials of any trade or urbanism—that give substance to Sharma's "feudalisation of commerce" or Kosambi's "feudal trade charters".

It is regrettable, therefore, to allege bluntly (p. 74) that Chattopadhyaya believes "in an unbroken and undisturbed urban tradition in early medieval India", "*without least realising* that his references to the decline of an overwhelming majority of urban centres indicate the general pattern of urbanisation" (emphasis added). The case for urban decline rests on "unassailable archaeological evidence", so says Thakur (p. 77), but the words were used thus by Chattopadhyaya first (op.cit., p. 216).

It is quite clear, and to his credit, that Thakur has examined the original sources used by Chattopadhyaya. This is what enables him to disagree with the latter's interpretations at many points. Some criticisms are made just for the sake of it, however, such as doubting the meaning of *maṇḍapikā* as customs house and of *vīthi* as a shop; he himself employs the latter meaning elsewhere in the book. What is discreditable is that Thakur has appropriated Chattopadhyaya's narrative, footnotes and all, in his own name (pp. 59-74). Moreover, Chattopadhyaya took some

pains to point out that Prthūdaka was not a "developed township", which Thakur attributes to him (p. 67); refuting what was never argued and pointing out what was already done, Thakur then adds insult to the injury: "a fact which Chattopadhyaya realises when he says that if at all it has to be given the label urban, it may at best be called an incipient urban centre" (p.61). It is also curious that Thakur's discussion of "the third urbanization" (pp. 90-96) should do without any reference to Chattopadhyaya's paper, "Urban Centres in Early Medieval India : An Overview" in S. Bhattacharya and R. Thapar, ed, *Situating Indian History* (Delhi, 1986), which is where the reviewer first came across the term (in a mimeographed copy in 1983).

While Thakur is welcome to his critique of Harbans Mukhia's views on labour availability, fertility of soil, subjection of peasantry, etc. (pp. 27, 30-35, 36-40), it seems unfair to criticize Mukhia (pp. 27-30, 35) for basing his statements on the generalizations made by our leading authorities (for example, R. S. Sharma on the break-up of big farms in the post-Gupta period) and for having not known the evidence we produced *after* his critique (big farms in early medieval India and more instances of the use of forced labour in production process). (That Mukhia's critique of Maurice Dobb has the same demerit is another matter.) In all fairness we should thank Mukhia for sharpening our focus on these matters. More important, on the marginal nature of the use of forced labour in production, Mukhia may still cite us in his own support, including Thakur ("we do not have much evidence of very large landed estates and extensive direct cultivation by the landlords in the early medieval context", p. 35) and the *revised* edition of *Indian Feudalism* (pp. 223-24).

M. R. Tarafdar has been treated in about the same way as Chattopadhyaya. It is one thing to detect logical errors in Tarafdar's account; it is quite another to lift his evidence, sentences and insights, then to provide them as fresh information to him to tell him how ill-informed and illogical he has been!

Despite everything, Thakur's capacity to reason critically comes right through the book. For an author who has so energetically defended R. S. Sharma's theses, it is indeed surprising to have bypassed the strictures of Vivekanand Jha ("Social Content of the *Bhagavadgītā*", *IHR*, Vol. XI, Nos 1-2, p. 37, fn. 6) on his own [Thakur's] paper on the *Bhagavadgītā*, included in this book as an appendix (pp. 104-18).

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LEE SIEGEL, *Laughing Matters: Comic Tradition in India* (Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1989). Pp. xxii+497. Rs 150.00.

This book is "an attempt to contribute to a broadened and deepened perception of Indian culture by revealing the ways in which India has laughed at itself" (p. xvi). It is a neglected area of research, particularly so because the author's chief source of information is printed Sanskrit literature. Dr Siegel states that his Indian informants were surprised by his "discovery" of the comic spirit in such an unlikely place. This apart, he has a good deal more to his credit. He has thoroughly surveyed the enormous corpus of Sanskrit literature, organized his material with meticulous care and treated his subject from every conceivable point of view — causal, functional and developmental.